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One-pot terpolymerization of CHO, CO₂ and L-lactide using chloride indium catalysts

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Ring-opening copolymerization reactions of epoxides, carbon dioxide and cyclic esters to produce copolymers is a promising strategy to prepare CO₂-based polymeric materials. In this contribution, bimetallic chloride indium complexes have been developed as catalysts for the copolymerization processes of cyclohexene oxide, carbon dioxide and L-lactide under mild reaction conditions. The catalysts displayed good catalytic activity and excellent selectivity towards the preparation of poly(cyclohexene carbonate) (PCHC) at one bar CO₂ pressure in the absence of a co-catalyst. Additionally, polyester-polycarbonate copolymers poly(lactide-co-cyclohexene carbonate) (PLA-co-PCHC) were obtained via one-pot one-step route without the use of a co-catalyst. The degree of incorporation of carbon dioxide can be easily modulated by changing the CO₂ pressure and the monomers feed, resulting in copolymers with different thermal properties.

Introduction

During the last few decades, the rapid depletion of fossil fuels and the stronger legislative requirements for a circular economy have driven the scientific and industrial community to search for greener and more sustainable catalytic processes to synthesize high value-added chemicals and polymers.^{1–5} Finding new biorenewable-based monomers to produce biodegradable polymeric materials has been targeted by many research groups around the world. In this context, carbon dioxide has emerged as a highly desirable renewable C1 chemical feedstock for the synthesis of polycarbonate materials due to its low toxicity and abundance.^{6–12} Among the different synthetic routes developed for their preparation, the ring-opening copolymerization (ROCOP) of epoxides and CO₂ is the most extensively studied reaction.^{6,13–16} Similarly, a lot of attention has been devoted to the synthesis of biodegradable aliphatic polyesters through the ring-opening polymerization (ROP) of cyclic esters.^{17–20} Polylactide (PLA), synthesized from the ROP of lactide, represents the most studied biodegradable polyester due to its relatively facile production from agricultural renewable sources, its biodegradability and biocompatibility, and it has already found numerous applications

ranging from food packaging to the biomedical and pharmaceutical industry (Scheme 1).^{18,21–25}

Scheme 1 Synthesis of polycarbonate, polyester-polyether and polyester-polycarbonate materials by different ROP and ROCOP processes.

A wide range of different metal complexes has been reported for the development of biodegradable polycarbonates, polyesters and terpolymers.^{6,14,26,27} Amongst them, it is worth highlighting the bimetallic zinc/magnesium β -diiminato (BDI) complexes, firstly described by Coates and co-workers.^{28,29} They were found to be very efficient for the stereoselective ROP of lactide, affording the formation of isotactic, heterotactic and syndiotactic PLA from *L*-, *rac*- and *meso*-lactide respectively.^{30,31} The introduction of electro-withdrawing groups in the imine moieties of the BDI ligands increased the catalytic activity of these complexes for the ROCOP/terpolymerization of different epoxides and CO₂, yielding the corresponding polycarbonate materials with high molecular weights and TOF values up to 5520 h⁻¹.³² In addition, their catalytic activity was further tested towards the terpolymerization reaction of epoxides, CO₂ and β -butyrolactone, affording the corresponding block polycarbonate-polyester copolymers with tuneable properties such as glass transition temperature or transparency.^{33,34}

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Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: experimental data, work-up for catalytic reactions, spectra of the ¹H and ¹³C{¹H} NMR and IR for complexes **1–4**, X-ray crystallographic data for compound **1** and ¹H and ¹³C NMR, IR and MALDI-ToF spectra, DSC and TGA of the corresponding polymers. See DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Scheme 2. Indium catalysts reported for epoxide and CO₂ copolymerization reactions

Bimetallic and heterobimetallic complexes supported by salen-type ligands have also been widely used for the ROCOP of different epoxides and CO₂ and their terpolymerization reactions with different lactones.^{35–50} In this context, a wide range of cobalt catalysts featuring chiral salen-type scaffolds were developed by Xiao Bing-Lu and co-workers' for the enantioselective synthesis of different polymeric materials.^{36,37,43–46}

Scorpionate metal complexes have been employed as catalysts for these processes.^{51–55} Recently, our research group reported a series of bimetallic heteroscorpionate zinc acetate complexes as catalysts for the ROCOP of CHO and CO₂ in the absence of a co-catalyst and at one bar of CO₂ pressure, and the terpolymerization reaction with phthalic anhydride, affording the corresponding polycarbonate-polyester material with tuneable PCHC content depending on the CO₂ pressure applied.⁵⁶

Indium complexes have proven to be highly active towards the ROP of lactide to afford PLA.^{57–62} Mehrhodavandi et al. reported the first chiral indium catalyst for the living ROP of cyclic esters.⁵⁸ It showed excellent catalytic activity for the living polymerization of *rac*-LA to produce isotactically enriched PLA with high molecular weights and narrow polydispersities. These catalysts were further investigated towards the polymerization of β -butyrolactone (BBL) and *meso*-LA, and their terpolymerization reaction to form di- and triblock copolymers, as well as star-shaped copolymers.^{59,63,64} On the other hand, indium complexes remain almost unknown for the copolymerization of epoxides and CO₂.^{65–67} In the last few years, the first salen-type indium catalysts for the ROCOP of epoxides and CO₂ were reported (Scheme 2a).⁶⁶ They showed great catalytic activity towards the synthesis of PCHC, with high selectivity and under one

bar CO₂ pressure, affording polymeric materials with narrow polydispersities and high molecular weights. New hemisalen H[PNN] indium complexes have also been tested as catalysts for the copolymerization of CHO and CO₂ along with different co-catalysts at 80 °C and 30 bar of CO₂, affording PCHC with molecular weights up to 10000 g mol⁻¹ and moderate to high selectivities (Scheme 2b).⁶⁷ This, combined with that the use of indium complexes as catalysts for the terpolymerization reactions of epoxides, CO₂ and cyclic esters to produce polyester-polycarbonate materials remains unknown, as far as we know, prompted us to consider the design of a new family of indium complexes which present activity in this terpolymerization reaction.

Herein, we report novel scorpionate indium complexes which have showed to be very efficient catalysts for the ROCOP reaction of CHO and CO₂ under mild reaction conditions and at one bar CO₂ pressure. Among the synthesized complexes, complex **1** has proved to be the most active catalyst, and its activity has been further tested towards the terpolymerization reaction of CHO, CO₂ and *L*-lactide to produce polyester-polycarbonate materials. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first indium complex ever reported for terpolymerization reactions involving *L*-lactide as monomer (Scheme 2c).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and structural characterization of catalysts

Bimetallic chloride indium complexes [InCl₂{(κ³-bpzbe)(μ-O)}]₂ (**1**), [InCl₂{(κ³-bpzte)(μ-O)}]₂ (**2**), [InCl₂{(κ³-bpzappe)(μ-O)}]₂ (**3**) and [InCl₂{(κ³-bpzFerr)(μ-O)}]₂ (**4**) were prepared in a two-step reaction by metathesis of the corresponding previously reported alcohol-containing heteroscorpionate ligand precursors 1,1-bis(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-3,3-dimethylbutan-2-ol (bpzbeH; L1), (2,2-bis(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-1-p-tolyl)ethan-1-ol (bpzteH; L2), (2,2-bis(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-1-(4-(dimethylamino)phenyl)-1phenylethan-1-ol (bpzappeH; L3) and the newly synthesized (2,2-bis(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-1-ferrocenyl)ethan-1-ol (bpzFerrH; L4), with one equivalent of indium trichloride in THF at room temperature (Scheme 3). Ligand L1-L4 were chosen in order to study the influence of an aromatic, a bulkier alkyl group, or a ferrocene moiety on the catalytic activity and selectivity of the indium complexes towards the synthesis of polycarbonates and/or terpolymer materials. Complexes **1-4** were isolated in high yields and showed to be stable in solution and under air conditions in solid state.

The structural characterization of these compounds was performed by different spectroscopic techniques. The ¹H and ¹³C{¹H}-NMR spectra for complexes **1-4** exhibited two distinct sets of resonances for protons and carbons of both pyrazole rings, indicating they were not equivalent (Fig. 1). This fact was attributed to the presence of a stereogenic centre in the C^a carbon of the ligand L1-L4 precursors. These data indicate the possible existence of four stereoisomers (two diastereoisomers) for indium complexes (Fig. 1). Thus, the VT NMR analysis shows one diastereoisomer at -93 °C in which the two heteroscorpionate ligands are equivalent. NOESY-1D NMR experiments and ¹H-¹³C heteronuclear correlation (g-HSQC) permitted the unequivocal assignment of most of the resonances.

Based on the data obtained, an octahedral disposition for dinuclear indium complexes with the heteroscorpionate ligand in a κ^3 -NNO- μ -O coordination mode with the ligand bridging the two indium centres can be proposed (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Synthesis of chloride indium complexes 1-4.

Fig. 1. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of $[\text{InCl}_2\{(\kappa^3\text{-bpzFerr})(\mu\text{-O})\}_2]$ **4** in CD_3CN .

The solid-state structure of these compounds was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis for complex **1**. The corresponding ORTEP diagram is represented in Fig. 2. The crystallographic data and selected bond distances and angles are collected in Tables S1 and S2 respectively. The molecular structure revealed a dimeric compound in which each indium centre displays an octahedral geometry with the heteroscorpionate ligands coordinated in a κ^3 -NNO fashion, two chloride atoms disposed in a cis-configuration and the last position of the coordination sphere occupied by the oxygen atom from the alkoxide group of the second heteroscorpionate ligand, which also acts as bridging atom between both indium centres. Bond distances between the indium and the chloride atoms adopt values of 2.407(2) Å and 2.415(1) Å, which are slightly shorter than the ones found for other indium chloride complexes.^{68,69} Also, bond distances between the indium and nitrogen atoms of 2.267(5) Å for the $\text{In}(1)\text{-N}(1)$ bond and 2.371(4) Å for the $\text{In}(1)\text{-N}(3)$ bond, are slightly longer than those found for other indium complexes with scorpionate ligands.^{68,69} Bond angles confirmed the proposed distorted octahedral structure, with the maximum distortion of 162.2(2)° observed for the $\text{O}(1\text{A})\text{-In}(1)\text{-N}(1)$ angle.

ROCOP of Cyclohexene Oxide and CO_2

A first screening to evaluate the catalytic activity of complexes **1-4** was performed for the ROCOP reaction of CHO and CO_2 . The initial

experiments were carried out using 0.5 mol% of catalyst, at 60 °C and 40 bar of CO_2 without the use of a co-catalyst under solvent free conditions (Scheme 4), and the results are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram for complex $[\text{InCl}_2\{(\kappa^3\text{-bpzbe})(\mu\text{-O})\}_2]$ (**1**). Hydrogen atoms are omitted. Thermal ellipsoids are shown at 30%.

Scheme 4. Synthesis of poly(cyclohexene carbonate) (**5**) catalyzed by complexes **1-4**.^a

Chloride indium complexes **1** and **3** with tert-butyl groups and dimethylamino substituted aromatic rings respectively, displayed high catalytic activity and excellent selectivity towards the synthesis of PCHC. On the other hand, complex **4** exhibited moderate activity, attributed to electronic and steric effects of the ferrocene moiety. Surprisingly, complex **2**, featuring a toluene substituent in the alcohol group, showed no catalytic activity, which was ascribed to the insolubility of the catalyst in CHO. It is worth highlighting that no co-catalyst was used, indicating that chloride indium complexes catalyzed the reaction efficiently themselves. In addition, no formation of polyether or trans-cyclic carbonate was observed in any case, indicating the absence of homopolymerization or back-biting side-reactions. A control experiment using 1 mol% of InCl_3 as catalyst under the same reaction conditions was carried out and no catalytic activity was observed in this entry (Table 1, entry 5). Among all the complexes tested, complex **1** was selected as the optimal catalyst to conduct the copolymerization reaction, achieving 77% conversion and a selectivity higher than 99% (Table 1, entry 1). Thus, it was further used for the optimization of the reaction temperature, CO_2 pressure and reaction time (See Fig. 3-5 and SI). As it can be seen from Fig. 3, the temperature showed to have a great influence on the catalytic activity of complex **1**, which remained almost constant in the range of temperatures 60-100 °C but decreased notably to 25 % when the temperature was decreased to 50 °C. On the other hand, the selectivity of the process remained almost constant for all the range of temperatures tested, decreasing to 95% when the reaction temperature was increased to 100 °C, at which the formation of trans-cyclohexene carbonate by-product is observed.

Table 1. Synthesis of PCHC (5) catalyzed by complexes 1-4.

Entry	Catalyst	Conv. (%) ^b	Carbonate linkages (%) ^b	Polycarbonate selectivity (%) ^b	$M_{n,exp.}^c$ (g/mol)	PDI ^c
1	1	77	>99	>99	5340	1.30
2	2	-	-	-	-	-
3	3	72	>99	>99	4930	1.21
4	4	26	>99	>99	1150	1.28
5	InCl₃	-	-	-	-	-

^aCopolymerisation conditions: 25 μ mol of catalyst; [CHO]:[catalyst] = 200:1, 16 hours, 60 $^{\circ}$ C, 40 bar CO₂. ^bDetermined by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy of the crude reaction mixture through the comparison of the integrals of signals arising from the methylene protons in the ¹H NMR spectra due to copolymer carbonate linkages against copolymer ether linkages and *trans*-cyclic carbonate. ^cDetermined by GPC using polystyrene standards in THF.

Fig. 3. Effect of the reaction temperature on the catalytic activity of complex 1.

The effect of the CO₂ pressure was then investigated at the optimal reaction temperature of 60 $^{\circ}$ C, and the results are shown in Fig. 4. It is worth highlighting that complex 1 showed to be active for the copolymerization process even at one bar CO₂ pressure, achieving 47% conversion and a selectivity higher than 99% towards the formation of PCHC (5). The selectivity of the process remained constant for all the range of pressures tested and the catalytic performance of complex 1 increased as the pressure increased, reaching 77% conversion at 40 bar CO₂.

Fig. 4. Effect of the reaction pressure on the catalytic activity of complex 1.

In order to maximize the sustainability of the process and perform the copolymerization under the mildest reaction conditions, the reaction temperature and pressure were set at 60 $^{\circ}$ C and one bar

CO₂ pressure, respectively. Then, the effect of the reaction time on the copolymerization process was also studied (Fig. 5), obtaining TOF values ranging from 4 to 11 h⁻¹ for reaction times between 1 and 24 hours (Table 2). As it can be seen, the conversion increased linearly until it reached 42% after 8 hours. Then, the conversion increased much slower reaching 52% after 24 hours, which can be attributed to mass transfer issues, due to the increase of the viscosity of the reaction mixture and the decreased concentration of CHO in the solution. Phosphasalen indium complexes previously described exhibited generally lower TOF values with longer reaction times.⁶⁶ Similarly, hemisalen H[NNO] indium complexes recently reported also exhibited lower TOF values, using harsher reaction conditions of 30 bar CO₂, 80 $^{\circ}$ C and 24 h.⁶⁷

Fig. 5. Effect of the reaction time on the catalytic activity of complex 1 at 1 bar CO₂.

The molecular weights of the polycarbonate materials synthesized increased as the conversion of the copolymerization process increased, obtaining in all cases narrow polydispersity values ranging from 1.15-1.21 (Table 2). Generally, the molecular weights obtained for the polycarbonate materials proved to be approximately five times lower than the theoretical values calculated from the conversion obtained (Table 2), which was indicative of the presence of water or cyclohexenediol acting as chain-transfer agents, and, thus, reducing the molecular weight of the polycarbonates obtained.^{66,70,71}

The polycarbonate materials synthesized were characterized by ¹H-NMR (Fig. S9) and ¹³C-{¹H}-NMR spectroscopy (Fig. S10), gel permeation chromatography (GPC) (see Supporting Information)

Table 2. Effect of the reaction time on the synthesis of poly(cyclohexene carbonate) (5) catalyzed by complex 1.^a

Entry	t (h)	Conv. (%) ^b	Carbonate linkages (%) ^b	TOF (h ⁻¹) ^c	$M_{n,theo.}^d$ (g/mol)	$M_{n,exp.}^e$ (g/mol)	PDI ^e
1	1	3	>99	4.6	653	-	-
2	2	9	>99	8.8	2556	-	-
3	3	15	>99	10.0	4260	850	1.21
4	4	20	>99	10.1	5680	1150	1.20
5	6	32	>99	10.7	9088	1800	1.20
6	8	42	>99	10.5	11928	2400	1.18
7	16	47	>99	6.0	13348	2865	1.16
8	24	52	>99	4.3	14768	3100	1.15
9	48	63	>99	2.6	17892	3590	1.19

^aCopolymerization conditions: 25 μ mol of complex; [CHO]:[1] = 200:1, 16 hours, 60 °C, one bar CO₂. ^bDetermined by ¹H-NMR from the reaction mixture; ^cTOF = (mol product) / (mol catalyst \times time); ^d $M_{n,theo.}$ = (monomer/initiator) \times (% conversion) \times (M_w CHC). ^eDetermined by GPC using polystyrene standards in TH

and matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-ToF MS) (Fig. 6 and Fig. S11). ¹³C-¹H-NMR study allowed to determine the tacticity of the synthesized polycarbonate materials. Thus, an atactic structure was proposed since both signals corresponding to the isotactic and syndiotactic dyads were detected.

The MALDI-ToF spectrum for PCHC (5) showed two end-group series of peaks with a m/z interval of 142 mass units, indicating a controlled alternating microstructure (Fig. 5). The major series (blue diamond) is in good agreement with a polymeric chain with one hydroxyl and carbonic acid end-groups in the polycarbonate material. A second major series (green diamond) also containing two hydroxyl end groups corresponding to *trans*-cyclohexanediol was observed, indicating the existence of chain transfer agents during the copolymerization, as expected due to the low molecular weights obtained for the polycarbonate materials synthesized.

Finally, the thermal properties of the polycarbonate material synthesized were determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). TGA showed that it is stable in the range of temperatures between 0-200 °C (Fig. S13), while differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) exhibited a T_g value at 65 °C (Fig. S14). This T_g value is lower than others found in the literature for atactic PCHC, attributed to the low molecular weights of the PCHC obtained.⁷²

Fig. 6. MALDI-ToF spectrum for PCHC (5) obtained by complex 1 (Table 2, entry 7).

Terpolymerization of Cyclohexene Oxide, CO₂ and L-lactide

The versatility of complex 1 was further investigated towards the terpolymerization reaction of CHO, CO₂ and L-LA to afford PLA-co-PCHC (6). To the best of our knowledge, only a few examples of zinc catalysts have ever been reported for this process, being complex 1 the first indium complex.⁷³⁻⁷⁶ However, some of these catalysts afforded the formation of block copolymers PLA-*b*-PCHC either by sequential addition methods or by tandem catalysis,^{75,76} and, in some cases, by different synthetic routes employing cyclohexene carbonate or L-lactide-O-carboxyanhydride as monomers.^{74,75}

The initial experiments were carried out under solvent-free conditions, at 60 °C and 40 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 hours, using [1]:[L-lactide]:[CHO] of 0.5-1.0:100:700 molar ratio (Scheme 5) (the catalysts loading is respect to L-LA monomer), and the results are given in Table 3 (entries 1 and 2). As it can be seen, an increase in the catalyst loading resulted in a higher CO₂ incorporation into the polymeric material, producing a higher PCHC content. On the other hand, the ROP of L-LA to afford poly(L-lactide) (PLA) was achieved quantitatively in both scenarios, which is indicative that the ROP of L-lactide is the first step in the terpolymerization process. In addition, no homopolymerization of CHO to produce poly(cyclohexene oxide) (PCHO) was observed in any case.

Scheme 5. Synthesis of terpolymers derived from CHO, L-LA and CO₂ catalyzed by complex 1.

Table 3. Influence of the pressure on the synthesis of terpolymer **6** catalyzed by complex **1**.^a

Entry	Pressure (bar)	Conv.(%) CHO ^c	Conv. (%) L-LA ^c	PLA (%) ^c	Ether linkages (%) ^c	Carbonate linkages (%) ^c
1 ^b	40	2.7	100	91	-	9
2	40	17	100	60	-	40
3	30	20	100	54	-	46
4	20	23	100	48	-	52
5	10	27	100	42	-	58
6	5	16	100	60	-	40
7	1	0	100	100	-	-

^aCopolymerization conditions: [CHO]:[L-LA]:[1] = 700:100:1, 16 h, 60 °C; ^b[CHO]:[L-LA]:[1] = 700:100:0.5, 16 h, 60 °C; ^cDetermined by ¹H-NMR from the reaction mixture.

Table 4. Influence of the [CHO]/[L-LA] ratio and thermal properties of the different PLA-PCHC (**6**) copolymers synthesized.^a

Entry	[CHO]:[L-LA] ratio	Conv.(%) CHO ^b	Conv. (%) L-LA ^b	PLA (%) ^b	Ether linkages (%) ^b	Carbonate linkages (%) ^b	<i>M_{n, exp.}</i> ^b (kg mol ⁻¹)	PDI ^b	<i>T_g</i> (°C) ^c	<i>T_{d,5%}</i> (°C) ^d
1	1:1	0	75	100	-	-	5.1	1.7	47	197
2	2:1	18	100	81	-	19	5.8	1.8	55	201
3	3:1	20	100	71	-	29	6.4	1.7	58	200
4	4:1	21	100	64	-	36	7.5	1.7	59	205
5	5:1	24	100	55	-	45	8.3	1.8	63	222
6	7:1	27	100	40	-	60	9.1	1.6	74	244

^aCopolymerization conditions: [L-LA]:[1] = 100:1, 16 h, 60 °C, 10 bar; ^bDetermined by ¹H-NMR from the reaction mixture. ^cDetermined by GPC using polystyrene standards in THF. ^dDetermined by Differential Scanning Calorimetry. ^eDetermined by Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA). Reported as temperature at 5% mass loss.

The effect of the reaction pressure on the terpolymerization process was then investigated using a catalyst loading of both 0.5 (Table S5) and 1.0 mol% (Table 3 and Table S6). The CO₂ pressure showed to have a significant effect on this process making it possible to modulate the polycarbonate content in the resulting terpolymer. The same trend was observed in both cases, with the highest PCHC content obtained at 10 bar CO₂. The increase of the reaction pressure resulted in a lower PCHC content in the resulting terpolymer, in agreement with previously reported results.⁷⁷ This can be ascribed to a dilution effect resulting from the increased amount of CO₂ in the reactor.

Once the [1] and CO₂ pressure were optimized to 1 mol% respect to the L-LA monomer and 10 bar respectively, the optimal [CHO]:[L-LA] ratio for the terpolymerization process was investigated and the results are presented in Table 4. When the [CHO]:[L-LA] ratio employed was 1:1, only 75% conversion of L-LA toward the formation of PLA was achieved (Table 4, entry 1) and no formation of polycarbonate was observed, giving hints of a mechanism in which the ROP of L-LA was proposed as the first step of the terpolymerization. The increase in the [CHO]:[L-LA] ratio resulted in the complete consumption of L-LA towards the formation of PLA and the increase of the polycarbonate content in the resulting terpolymer, with the highest PCHC content of 60% when the [CHO]:[L-LA] ratio employed was 7:1 (Table 4, entry 6).

The ¹H-NMR spectrum (Fig. 7 and S17) of the terpolymer materials synthesized exhibited two different sets of signals with high intensity corresponding to the PLA and the PCHC moieties and low intensity signals corresponding to chain end and junction groups. PLA exhibited a doublet at 1.57 ppm corresponding to the methyl group CH^a and a quartet at 5.17 ppm corresponding to the

methine proton CH^b. The latter is increasingly shifted as the amount of CHO in the reaction mixture increases (Fig. S18), which can be indicative of terpolymers with a statistical morphology. On the other, PCHC moiety exhibited five signals with high intensity corresponding to the methylene and methine groups of the cyclohexyl ring.⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶ ¹³C-{¹H}-NMR spectrum (Fig. S19) suggested the formation of a copolymer since different signals in the C=O region were observed, corresponding to both polycarbonate (154.3, 153.8 ppm) and polyester (169.6 ppm) moieties, in agreement with previously reported results.⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶ 2D-DOSY NMR spectroscopy confirmed the formation of only one polyester-polycarbonate (PLA-co-PCHC) copolymer, since only one diffusion coefficient was observed for all the signals (Fig. S20). The reactions showed progressively increasing molar masses with the PCHC content in the resulting terpolymer, achieving its maximum value at 9100 g mol⁻¹ (Table 4, Entry 6), corresponding with the highest CO₂ incorporation. PDI values remained almost constant in the range of 1.6-1.8 for all the ratios employed (Fig. S21-S23). However, low mass values can be ascribed due to the presence of transesterification reactions. The experimental data support that complex **1** first does a ROP of L-lactide followed by polycarbonate formation, although the presence of traces of water or diols in the reaction mixture can make both the initial PLA polymer and the subsequent PCHC chains scramble over time generating copolymers with different structures with low molecular weights. TGA analysis revealed that all terpolymers were stable in the range between 0-200 °C.

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Terpolymer with the highest [CHO]:[L-LA] ratio (Table 4, entry 6) showed to be stable up to 244 °C, due to the higher PCHC content. Glass transition temperatures for the different PLA-co-PCHC copolymers exhibit a single value between the one for pure PLA (ca 50 °C, depending on chain length) and pure PCHC (120 °C), which also sustains the premise of the formation of statistical copolymers. The T_g also increased as the [CHO]:[L-LA] ratio increased, and thus, with the polycarbonate content in the terpolymer, achieving its maximum value at 74 °C when a 7:1 molar ratio was applied (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum for PLA-co-PCHC (6) terpolymer in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 8. DSC traces for terpolymers using conditions described in Table 4.

In terms of the reaction mechanism, it is worth highlighting from the results obtained that the terpolymerization process proceeds in a different pathway compared to the previously reported mechanism for β -diiminate or salen-type catalysts (Scheme 6).

Different studies showed that the catalytic activity of the metal complex could be switched towards the polymerisation of one monomer or another depending on the CO_2 pressure.^{33,40,78,79} In the presence of high CO_2 pressures, only PCHC (5) was generated, which was assigned due to the rapid formation of the metal-carbonate group, which is not able to perform the ROP of the corresponding cyclic ester. However, in this work and as previously commented, the ROP of the *L*-lactide monomer occurs in the first place regardless the presence and pressure of CO_2 , and once all the monomer is converted to PLA, the ROCOP of CHO and CO_2 takes place. This is indicative of the high affinity of **1** to ring-open the cyclic ester and generate alkoxide species, even in the presence of CO_2 . In any case, this would lead to the formation of well-defined block copolymers, which does not correlate well with the presumably formation of statistical polymeric materials according to the data from the $^1\text{H NMR}$ and DSC spectra. As aforementioned, it could be assumed that, given the transesterification reactions occurring, the initial block structure can be scrambled over time to ultimately form a statistical copolymer. Therefore, although we are yet unsure on the precise mechanism operating with these catalysts, we have already gathered some relevant information that set the basis of our future mechanistic studies.

Conclusions

New dinuclear chloride indium complexes supported by heteroscorpionate ligands have been synthesized and characterized by different spectroscopic techniques. The solid structure of complex **1** has been confirmed by X-Ray diffraction analysis, showing an octahedral geometry for both indium atoms, with the heteroscorpionate ligand coordinated in a $\kappa^3\text{-NNO}$ mode, and with the oxygen atom from the alkoxide group acting also as bridging group between both indium centres.

Indium complexes **1-4** were tested as catalysts for the copolymerization reaction between CHO and CO_2 to afford poly(cyclohexene carbonate) **5** in the absence of a co-catalyst at 60 °C and 40 bar CO_2 pressure. Amongst them, complex **1** showed to be the most active, and its catalytic activity was further evaluated at one bar CO_2 pressure, affording PCHC in 52% conversion after 16 hours, with 99 % selectivity and TOF values up to 10.7 h^{-1} .

Scheme 6. Mechanisms for terpolymerisation of epoxides, CO₂ and lactones using: a) β-diimine and salen-type catalysts, b) heteroscorpionate indium 1 complex

Compound **1** was also found to be an efficient catalyst for the terpolymerization reaction of CHO, CO₂ and L-lactide, obtaining the corresponding polyester-polycarbonate material. Optimization of the reaction conditions was also carried out by performing experiments at different CO₂ pressures and CHO:L-lactide ratios. Results showed different CO₂ incorporation, making it easy to modulate the polycarbonate content in the resulting terpolymer depending on the CO₂ pressure applied. Thus, complex **1** represents the first indium complex ever reported for terpolymerization processes, which we hope will broaden the scope of this element within this topic and serve as inspiration for future works.

Experimental section

Experimental details and spectroscopic and crystallographic data for chloride indium complexes **1-4**, poly(cyclohexene carbonate) **5** and terpolymer **6** are provided in the Supporting Information. Representative procedure for the synthesis of [InCl₂{(κ³-bpzbe)(μ-O)}]₂ **1** is as follows:

[InCl₂{(κ³-bpzbe)(μ-O)}]₂ (**1**): In a 100 cm³ Schlenk tube, bpzbeH (1.00 g, 3.45 mmol) was dissolved in 30 mL of dry THF and cooled down to -78 °C. Then, a solution of ⁿBuLi (1.6M in hexanes, 2.30 mL, 3.62 mmol) was added dropwise and the mixture was maintained at -78 °C for one hour. After that time, the lithiated adduct was transferred via cannula to a pre-cooled slurry of InCl₃ (0.80 g, 3.62 mmol) in THF. The resulting mixture was warmed to room temperature and left stirring overnight. The white solid precipitated was filtered and dried in vacuo for two hours to afford complex **1** in 80% yield. Suitable crystals for X-Ray analysis were obtained from a CH₂Cl₂ solution at room temperature. ¹H-NMR (500MHz, CD₃CN, 298 K): δ = 6.18 (d, J_{HH} = 2.4 Hz, 1H, CH), 5.98 (s, 1H, H^{4,4'}), 5.92 (s, 1H, H^{4,4'}), 3.78 (d, J_{HH} = 2.3 Hz, 1H, C³H),

2.45, 2.41 (s, 6H, Me^{3,3'}), 2.32 (brs, 6H, Me^{5,5'}), 0.68 (s, 9H, ^tBu). ¹³C-{¹H}-NMR (125MHz, CD₃CN, 298 K): 151.3, 150.5, 141.4, 139.4 (C^{3,3'}, C^{5,5'}), 107.8, 106.6 (C^{4,4'}), 86.0 (C^a), 64.4 (CH), 36.3 (C-^tBu), 26.1 (^tBu), 13.6 (Me^{3,3'}), 11.7, 11.1 (Me^{5,5'}). Elemental analysis calcd. (%) for C₃₂H₅₀Cl₂In₂N₈O₂: C, 43.7; H, 5.7; N, 12.7; found: C, 43.9; H, 5.8; N, 12.5.

General procedure for ROCOP of CHO-CO₂ at high CO₂ pressure

Cyclohexene oxide (0.50 g, 5.09 mmol) and catalysts **1-4** (25.18 μmol) were placed into a stainless-steel reactor equipped with a magnetic stirrer bar in the glovebox. The autoclave was sealed, pressurized to 5 bar with CO₂, heated to the desired temperature and then pressurized to 10-40 bar with CO₂. The reaction mixture was subsequently stirred at 25–100 °C for 16 h. The conversion of cyclohexene oxide into poly(cyclohexene carbonate) **5** was determined by analysis of the crude reaction mixture by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy. Polymers were isolated by precipitation using MeOH to yield white powders. The solid was filtered and dried to constant weight.

General procedure for ROCOP of CHO-CO₂ at 1 bar CO₂ pressure

In the glovebox, chloride indium complex **1** (25.18 μmol) was dissolved in cyclohexene oxide (0.50 g, 5.09 mmol) under N₂ atmosphere in a Schlenk flask equipped with a stirring bar. The Schlenk flask was sealed, brought outside the glovebox and connected into a vacuum-CO₂ line. The reaction mixture was then purged with three cycles of vacuum-CO₂ and heated at 60 °C under one bar of CO₂ pressure, for the desired time (2-24h). The conversion of cyclohexene oxide into poly(cyclohexene carbonate) **5** was determined by analysis of the crude reaction mixture by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy. Polymers were isolated by precipitation using MeOH to yield white powders. The solid was filtered and dried to constant weight.

General procedure for the ROCOP of CHO, L-LA and CO₂

In the glovebox, complex **1** (25.18–50.09 μmol), cyclohexene oxide (5.09–35.63 mmol) and *L*-lactide (5.09 mmol) were placed into a stainless-steel reactor with a magnetic stirrer bar. The autoclave was sealed, pressurized to 5 bar with CO_2 , heated to the desired temperature and then pressurized to 5–40 bar with CO_2 . The reaction mixture was subsequently stirred at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 16 h. Then, the conversion and the selectivity were determined by NMR. The viscous mixture was then dissolved in the minimum amount of dichloromethane and precipitated with an excess of methanol. The polymer was filtered and dried to afford **6** as white powder.

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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